

PERFORMANCE INDICATORS AND SIGNIFICANCE OF A 5 kW·h MINI PHOTOVOLTAIC STATION IN THE “SUNNY HOUSEHOLD”

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Abstract. *This article examines the special attention paid to the development of solar energy in our country, revealing the prospects and advantages of solar energy, as well as the specifics of alternative energy production. Statistical data on the performance of a 5 kWh mini-photovoltaic station installed in the "Solar House" regarding the use of solar energy are presented.*

Keywords: *sun, solar radiation, solar energy, solar power, solar house, solar panel, mini photovoltaic station, electricity, electricity consumer, consumption, sunny day, 8 hours, income.*

Introduction

It is well known to all of us that the demand for electric power is increasing day by day not only in our Republic but also on a global scale. If we take the last five years as an example, worldwide demand for electricity has been increasing by 50% each year. This necessitates the expansion and development of non-traditional and alternative energy sources. According to data from the International Energy Agency, if the use of solar energy continues to grow at the current pace, by the year 2050 it will be possible to meet 25% of the world's electricity demand through solar energy. At the same time, this would reduce the annual emission of carbon dioxide into the environment by 6 billion tons.

The radiation of the light flux coming from the center of the Sun, which is located at a distance of 1 astronomical unit (150×10^6 km) from our planet Earth, amounts to 1360 W/m^2 on a surface of 1 m^2 placed perpendicularly to it (outside the Earth's atmosphere). If we take into account the absorption of solar radiation by the Earth's atmosphere, then the radiation of the light flux on a 1 m^2 surface at sea level (at the equator and nearby regions) equals 1020 W/m^2 . The average daily value of the radiation of the light flux is roughly three times less due to the alternation of day and night and the varying angle of the Sun relative to the horizon. It is evident from this that the efficiency of the solar panels currently in use does not exceed 15–20%. It should also be noted that solar radiation is absorbed not only by the atmosphere but also by the lithosphere and hydrosphere.

Over the course of a year, the Earth's atmosphere, lithosphere, and hydrosphere absorb 3.85×10^{24} J of solar energy. Considering that $1 \text{ kW}\cdot\text{h} = 3,600,000 \text{ J}$, the total absorbed solar energy for the whole Earth amounts to $1.07 \times 10^{18} \text{ kW}\cdot\text{h}$, which represents an enormous amount of energy for humanity. The working principle of a device that converts solar radiation into electric power is as follows: the device that converts solar radiation into electricity is called a photoelement (a semiconductor device). Of the photoelements in use, 85% are silicon-based (Si), about 10% are

made from cadmium telluride (CdTe) crystals. The remaining portion consists of germanium (Ge), indium phosphide (InP), and gallium arsenide (GaAs) crystals.

Photoelements were first used in space, namely in artificial satellites, and have since been adapted for human needs under terrestrial conditions.

The entire electricity demand of artificial satellites is supplied precisely by solar energy. A photoelement consists of positively and negatively charged layers that create an electric field. The light flux (a stream of photon particles) falling on the photoelement knocks out electrons from it, and these electrons, passing through the electric field, generate an electric current. When the electric current reaches the inverter, electrical energy is produced and delivered to the power source. Various electric appliances that operate on electric current—such as light bulbs, refrigerators, vacuum cleaners, televisions, radios, others are connected to this source and can be used for human needs as required.

In the climate of Uzbekistan, there are approximately 260–270 sunny days per year, with each sunny day lasting about 8–10 hours. Taking this into account, we have significant potential to make maximum use of solar energy. At the current stage of global development, the growing demand for electricity and the continuous increase in energy prices make it crucial to develop green energy using modern, environmentally friendly, energy-efficient technologies and renewable energy sources. In this regard, practical work is being carried out in our Republic, and efforts are underway to further its development.

For instance, a 100 MW photovoltaic power station (PPS) has been built and commissioned in Karmana district of Navoi Region, and a wind power station (WPS) has been constructed and launched in the city of Zarafshan. In the Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022–2026, adopted by our government, special attention has been given to the development of “green” energy across our country.

Taking this into account, the leadership of our nation is encouraging individuals and legal entities to install solar panels and is providing support to accelerate this process. Numerous incentives and subsidies have been allocated, and surplus energy generated is purchased by the state at a high price. At present, 1 kW·h of electricity supplied to households is sold at a price of 600 UZS. Meanwhile, the state guarantees to purchase any surplus electricity generated by households from solar panels, wind power, or micro-hydropower plants at a rate of 1,000 UZS per 1 kW·h for at least 10 years, and this policy is already being implemented in practice.

This initiative was announced during a video conference meeting chaired by our President on June 10, 2022. If a household installs solar panels with a capacity of 5 kW, it can produce at least 25–30 kW·h of electricity per day. Below, we present the data on the performance of a 5 kW·h mini photovoltaic station installed at House No. 66, Ma’rifat Street, Navoi city, showing the amount of electricity, it generated over 50 days starting from the day of its initial installation:

	Date (Year, Month, Day)	Energy Produced (kW·h)	Remarks / Notes
1	21-July, 2025	15	The daily electricity consumption has not been taken into account in
2	22- July, 2025	20	
3	23- July, 2025	22	

4	24- July, 2025	42	the electrical energy data shown here.	
5	25- July, 2025	25		
6	26- July, 2025	19		
7	27- July, 2025	0		
8	28- July,2025	47		
9	29- July,2025	0		
10	30- July,2025	46		
11	31- July, 2025	0		
12	1-Avgust, 2025	0		
13	2-Avgust, 2025	0		
14	3-Avgust, 2025	17		
15	4-Avgust, 2025	23		
16	5-Avgust, 2025	0		
17	6-Avgust, 2025	41		
18	7-Avgust, 2025	23		
19	8-Avgust, 2025	0		
20	9-Avgust, 2025	22		
21	10-Avgust,2025	0		
22	11-Avgust, 2025	23		
23	12-Avgust, 2025	44		
24	13-Avgust, 2025	21		
25	14-Avgust, 2025	24		
26	15-Avgust,2025	0		
27	16-Avgust, 2025	43		
28	17-Avgust, 2025	22		
29	18-Avgust, 2025	22		
30	19-Avgust,2025	0		
31	20-Avgust, 2025	20		
1	21-Avgust, 2025	42		The daily consumed electrical energy has not been taken into account in the electrical energy shown here.
2	22-Avgust,2025	20		
3	23-Avgust, 2025	0		
4	24-Avgust, 2025	37		
5	25-Avgust, 2025	21		
6	26-Avgust, 2025	19		
7	27-Avgust, 2025	20		
8	28-Avgust,2025	0		
9	29-Avgust, 2025	21		
10	30-Avgust, 2025	42		
11	31-Avgust,2025	8		
12	1-September, 2025	11		
13	2- September, 2025	17		
14	3- September,2025	0		
15	4- September,2025	19		

16	5- September,2025	0	
17	6- September,2025	19	
18	7- September,2025	19	
19	8- September,2025	34	
20	9- September, 2025	19	
21	10- September, 2025	0	
	Total	949 kW·h	

At present, 1 kW·h of electricity supplied to households is sold at a price of 600 UZS. Meanwhile, the state guarantees to purchase any surplus electricity generated by households from solar panels, wind power, or micro-hydropower plants at a rate of 1,000 UZS per 1 kW·h for at least 10 years, and this policy is already being implemented in practice.

Conclusion

This initiative was announced during a video conference meeting chaired by our President on June 10, 2022. If a household installs solar panels with a capacity of 5 kW, it can produce at least 25–30 kW·h of electricity per day. Below, we present the data on the performance of a 5 kW·h mini photovoltaic station installed at House N. 66, Marifat Street, Navoi city, showing the amount of electricity, it generated over 50 days starting from the day of its initial installation:

Considering the 25-year warranty period provided by the solar panel manufacturers, electricity generation in this field is not only environmentally harmless but also quite promising in terms of future prospects.

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